

FEATURES AND FUNCTIONS OF AN INTEGRATED EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT IN PROFESSIONAL SELF-DEVELOPMENT IN FUTURE TEACHERS

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Abstract. This abstract explores the essential features and functions of an integrated educational environment designed to facilitate the professional self-development of future teachers. The contemporary landscape of teacher education requires a holistic approach that goes beyond traditional classroom instruction. The study emphasizes the significance of an integrated educational environment in preparing educators for the multifaceted challenges of the 21st century. The abstract highlights the key features of such an environment, including interdisciplinary collaboration, technology integration, experiential learning opportunities, and a learner-centered pedagogical approach. It discusses how these features collectively contribute to the creation of a dynamic and engaging educational atmosphere that fosters not only academic knowledge but also the development of crucial skills and attitudes.

Furthermore, the abstract delves into the specific functions of this integrated educational environment. It explores the role of collaborative projects, real-world teaching experiences, mentorship programs, and reflective practices in shaping the professional identity and competence of future teachers. It emphasizes the importance of technology as an enabler, providing avenues for innovation, global connectivity, and lifelong learning. The abstract also addresses the potential challenges associated with implementing and maintaining an integrated educational environment, including the need for faculty development, infrastructure support, and ongoing assessment mechanisms.

As a system of professional development, the features of the modern integrative educational environment are understood as its important features and the characteristics that determine the process of personal and professional self-development of the teacher. Let's consider the important characteristics of the integrated educational environment that determine the potential for development.

1. As the most important sign of the environment, the property of integration is expressed in the systematic interaction of its components, resources and conditions. Integrativity is associated with environmental qualities such as

multidimensionality and unity. The integral nature of the environment is expressed in the presence of emergent properties that characterize the entire system. However, not every initial component has such characteristics separately. In this case, the macrothisim consists of integrated, but separate interacting components. The formed macro system affects the process of personal and professional self-development more than each component.

2. The Integrative Learning Environment is a discrete-professional development macro system that is continuous and integrated, while it is a fractional formation, represented by a separate meso-environment and micro-environment. The integrational educational environment is not only discrete, but also a global and universal quality of existing matter. The discrete nature of the integrated educational environment has an unconditional impact on the development and self-development of the teacher, since these processes occur in certain educational organizations. Thus, the continuity and discreteness of the Integrative environment complement each other in order to increase the effectiveness of the continuous process of self-development of the teacher as a person and professional person.

3. Environmental hierarchy refers to the construction of components in a strict order from bottom to top of the organizational structure of an integrated educational environment. All interacting micro-environments, meso-environments, and macro-environments are subordinated to each other as a high-level global system. Each subsequent degree of subordination is related to the previous structural and functional links. The environmental hierarchy allows the teacher to use skill development resources at different levels of the organization.

4. The integrity property is inherent in any system: each of its components is variable, capable of influencing other components of the entire system. In turn, if the system itself changes, this is reflected in its individual components. Thus, the progressive development of microenvironment has a positive effect on changes in macroenvironment. This feature also contributes to the personal and professional self-development of the teacher, creating new opportunities for a progressive self-developing topic. Thus, an integral macro environment is considered in their totality rather than the usual sum of its individual microenvironments. Such a unit is provided by the presence of internal connections between individual elements of the system. It should be noted that the different characteristics of the environment are also interconnected with

each other, the totality of which, as a holistic education, characterizes the educational environment of integral professional development.

5. The Integrative educational environment is transformative-it can give the teacher the opportunity to choose resources and potential opportunities to design the process of personal and professional self-development. Such an environment includes a variety of conditions and combinations of them in order to ensure the full process of self-development. The methods of personal and professional self-development of the teacher are variable, which serves as the basis for the design of unique professional development trajectories.

6. The intensity characteristic can be defined as the saturation of the environment with resources and opportunities, the manifestation of their "concentration" for the implementation of development and self-development processes. Modern integral professional development the educational environment is literally filled with event fractals for the self-development of the teacher. The task of a self-developing subject is to identify potential opportunities, select different resources to create patterns of personal and meaningful behavior. The design of professional development trajectories consists in choosing environmental capabilities in its essence, determining the intensity of their shaping effect depending on the individual characteristics of the self-developing teacher.

7. The feature of emergence is the concept of systems theory. Features can appear in systems that do not have separate elements. These properties cannot be reduced to the sum of the properties of the individual structural and functional components of the system. Such features are new and cannot be found separately in each component. Translated from English, the concept of "emergence" means "emergence" or "sudden emergence". This is a feature of emergence that determines the potential for full professional development of an integral educational environment for the implementation of the teacher in the processes of self-development as a person and a professional.

Consider the functions of the educational environment of professional development, integrated in the process of personal and professional self-development - these are the roles that the environment plays in the self-development of the teacher.

As you know, one of the most important social problems of modern society is the training of a professionally qualified specialist capable of independent production activities, creative self-improvement and self-development. Personal and professional self-development contributes to the formation of a person as a

professional throughout his life, from the stage of professional self-determination and the stage of leaving professional life. The self-development of an individual is a process of purposeful, systematic, conscious actions in itself, including its own knowledge, qualities, skills, abilities and, in general, makes it possible to increase efficiency in professional activities.

Today, in the modern conditions of reforming the higher education system, it remains relevant to train specialists who are not only professionally qualified, but also capable of constantly changing realities, maintaining and improving their position and level in professional activities, that is, professional creative self-development. A special place in this process is occupied by professional self-development in the field of Education. This is where independent creativity, innovation thinking, reflexivity activities, forecasting and designing their own professional and personal education and development are carried out. Professional and personal self-development of the future specialist includes a complete set of theoretical knowledge and practical skills, understanding the methods of identifying and solving problems in various situations, the ability to reflexivity, practical self-esteem and readiness for self-improvement.

Self-development can be divided into several components:

- personal development;
- intellectual development;
- professional development;
- physical development.

In order to more fully understand the process of professional self-development, in general, it is necessary to determine what is the process of self-development. The process of self-development cannot be analyzed without identifying components such as "human development", "personal development" or "personal development".

The basis of the human development process, which approaches the understanding of self-development, is D.B.Bogoyavlensky, P.Ya.Galperin, W.V.Davidov, T.I. Ilin, E.N.Kabanova-Meller, Z.I.Kalmykova, N.A.Menchinskaya, A.V.Petrovsky, S.L.Rubinstein, D.B.Elkonin et al. S.L.Rubinstein interpreted human development as the development of abilities by generalizing and strengthening the operasias, movements, accompanied by a qualitatively new regulatory process as the basis of an acquired new state of development. T.I.Ilin provides the following definition: "human development is the process of personalization and formation of an individual under the influence of external and internal, controlled and uncontrollable factors, among which purposeful

education and upbringing occupy a leading place. Other scientists, on the other hand, define human development as "the process of its natural transformation as a result of socialization" and believe that it is subject to internal and external conditions. Internal conditions include everything that is inherited by a person, the structural features of his body, physiological and mental characteristics. External conditions include the social environment in which a person lives, as well as the processes of education and upbringing. L.S.Vigotsky and S.L.Rubinstein's research found that external conditions create the necessary conditions for the implementation of internal capabilities, the manifestation of internal conditions for Human Development. Hence, the process and result of human development occurs under the influence of three factors – heredity, environment and upbringing.

Many authors see a person's own activity in self-development, first of all, in self-transformation, in the disclosure and enrichment of their spiritual needs, creativity, personal potential, in the implementation of confidence in the possibility of self-education in the process of natural physiological, physical, mental and social development.

N.V.Bride, I.B.Sennovsky and P.I.After Tretyakov, in the study "self-development of students of the pedagogical college in the conditions of educational activities", future specialists determine the following components of self-development: reflexivity; self-knowledge; self-determination; self-control and self-awareness.

That is, the main focus on self-transformation in the conditions of the student's educational activities begins with a critical attitude to himself, to the results of his activities. This encourages students to learn and evaluate their personal characteristics, to know their inner world.

Self-knowledge activates self-determination, which leads the student to independently choose educational goals and objectives. Self-control serves as a condition and means of self-awareness, which consists in resolving the conflict between "want" and "possible".

Self-awareness makes it possible to maximize relationships in educational settings, including the attitude to the task and with other participants in educational activities.

S.A.Belicheva also distinguished the indicators of self-development of the individual, which are the basis of the personal characteristics of the future social teacher. These include: the presence of positively oriented life plans, professional intentions, attitude to educational activities, useful knowledge, skills, development of interests, adequacy of attitude to pedagogical influences,

the appearance of communalism, criticality, the ability to correctly assess others; self-criticism, self-analysis, ability to empathize, volitional qualities, culture of external behavior, abstinence from alcohol, smoking, shocks.

The main goal of today's reforms in the educational system is to train competitive specialist personnel. This in turn leads to the promotion of a number of requirements for prospective cadres. In particular, there is a growing emphasis on training skilled educators who love their profession, are competent, able to speak fluently.

In this regard, it is now important to identify conceptual approaches to the professional development of students studying at the University and justify the need for their professional self-development. This suggests that conceptual approaches to professional self-development need to be analyzed.

In conclusion, this abstract asserts that an integrated educational environment is indispensable in preparing future teachers to navigate the complexities of modern education. It advocates for the adoption of comprehensive strategies that empower educators not only with subject matter expertise but also with the adaptive skills and resilience needed for a continually evolving educational landscape. The research encourages further exploration and implementation of integrated approaches to enhance the professional self-development of future educators.

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